

GRADUONYMIC RELATIONS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE WORD "ANGER"

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Abstract: This article discusses the idea that phraseological units expressing the seme “anger” occupy an important place in the emotional-expressive layer of the language, that these units express the mental state of a person to different degrees and create graduonymic relations based on mutual semantic proximity. There is information about semantic relations between units related to the states of intensification and decrement in the process of gradation. The fact that graduonymic relations in phraseologisms with the seme “anger” reveal the internal semantic hierarchy of the phraseological system is proven by examples.

Keywords: anger, semantic change, linguistic analysis, phraseological gradation, semantic hierarchy; phraseological unit, graduonymic, semantic gradation, metaphor, emotional-expressiveness;

It is known that the vocabulary of the language consists of phraseologisms in addition to words. Phraseologisms are reflected in speech in a ready-made form and are presented to the listener. Phraseologisms serve to have a good effect on the listener, to give aesthetic pleasure. They increase the effectiveness of the speaker's speech. Even in phrases that are close in meaning, the gradation of plurals is clearly noticeable. Phraseologisms ensure that speech is fluent and clear. There are many phraseological units about the human mental state in the Uzbek language and they are found in literary works. In particular, it can be observed that words have a semantic relationship of mutual gradation, as noted in a number of linguistic studies.

Graduonymy is a systematic ranking of units (words or phraseologisms) belonging to the same semantic field based on increasing or decreasing meaning. Its important features are as follows:

It is a phenomenon inherent in the language system, expresses a semantic relationship, has a degree (intensity) between units, is close to synonymy, but is not completely synonymous.

For example, in the sema “anger”:

to get angry → to get angry → to boil → to explode;

Here, the units are arranged in increasing order based on the same sema (anger) — this

is gradation.

Gradation is a method of sequentially placing units in speech (often in a literary style) to enhance or reduce meaning or effect. Its characteristics:

It is distinguished by the fact that it is a speech phenomenon (stylistic device), the purpose is to increase impact, it is often used in a literary text, and it is consciously structured by the author.

For example, First he got angry, then his blood boiled, and finally he exploded.

Here, the author describes anger in a gradual manner — this is gradation.

Signs	Graduonymy	Gradation
Nature	Language system phenomenon	Speech (stylistic) phenomenon
Function	To show the gradation of meaning	To enhance the effect
Use	In the lexical/semantic system	In text and speech

So, since graduonymy is a system of gradation in a language, and gradation is a method of using gradation in speech, linguist J. Dzhumabayeva, distinguishing the concept of gradation from graduonymy, points out that the term stylistic gradation expresses the strengthening or weakening of the figurative meanings of a phrase, metaphor, or metonymic used within a single text, and graduonymy is generally a linguistic phenomenon that reflects the relationship of words based on denotative gradation [1]. Graduonymic relations are manifested by the gradual strengthening of the meaning of phraseological units. That is, the intensity level differs between units expressing the same seme, and they form a semantic sequence. Below we will see that phraseological units expressing the seme “anger” occupy an important place in the emotional-expressive layer of the language, these units express a person’s mental state to different degrees, creating graduonymic relations based on mutual semantic proximity.

For example, the following phraseological units expressing anger in the Uzbek language can be seen as a graduonymic series:

“To come out of anger” - a relatively mild degree of anger: You know how to take advantage of me at the beginning of the month and pay your money at the beginning of the promise!” - said the man, seeming to be a little bitter¹[2]

¹ Sadriddin Ayniy. Sudxo‘rning o‘limi. www.ziyouz.com kutubxonasi

“Getting angry” – moderate anger: Boots approached and stood motionless in front of me. I was furious. What are they watching, is there a circus here!..² [3]

“Blood boiling” – intense anger: His father’s eyes flashed under his thick eyebrows. Now his blood was boiling, his nerves, which used to punish those who disobeyed his orders, were starting to twitch.³ [4]

“To lose control” is a state of anger that is out of control: “What!” I could not control myself from anger and threw myself at him with a fist, I tried to raise my hand, but I didn't dare to hit him.⁴ [3]

These units belong to the same semantic field, each of which represents different stages of intensity of anger. This indicates the existence of a graduonymic system.

Also, metaphorical images play an important role in phraseologisms expressing anger. For example:

“Blood boils” (heat/temperature metaphor),

“Fire enters” (fire metaphor),

“Fire comes out of the eyes” (explosion and strong energy metaphor).

These images describe the intensification of anger and increase the expressiveness of graduonymic relations.

In conclusion, graduonymic relations in phraseological units with the meaning of anger serve to deepen understanding of the semantic system of the language and reveal the wealth of emotional-expressive means.

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² Chingiz Aytmatov “Sarvqomat dilbarim. Ilm-ziyo-zakovat. Toshkent – 2020.6 b

³ O‘tkir Hoshimov “Bahor qaytmaydi” “Sharq” nashriyot-matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosh tahririyati. Toshkent – 2005. 128 b.

⁴ Chingiz Aytmatov “Sarvqomat dilbarim” Ilm-ziyo-zakovat. Toshkent – 2020.31 b.